

THE USE OF DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS IN ANALYZING THE PERCEPTION OF OCCUPATIONAL RISKS: THE CASE OF SILICA DUST EXPOSURE AMONG CONSTRUCTION WORKERS

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Abstract: *Silica dust is present on the construction sites during digging, demolition, and cutting of wood and tiles. With no smell and no color, silica dust can cause various diseases, where silicosis represents the most common disease, with no cure. Preventive measures and medical exams are essential to reduce the risk of silica. The aim of this research is to assess how construction workers perceive the level of awareness, risk perception, and use of PPE related to occupational exposure to silica dust through the use of survey and descriptive statistical analysis. This study surveyed 55 male construction workers in Novi Sad to assess their awareness of risks related to silica dust exposure. The outcome of the study revealed that approximately 50% of employees described their understanding as minimal while the majority did not know about silicosis health risks. The majority of participants confirmed that they used safety masks but a significant portion reported using unsuitable protection and experiencing discomfort from this safety measure. According to the study results more than 60% of workers did not receive training from their employers regarding silica dust dangers. The results indicate that enhanced education alongside better personal protective equipment implementation would boost workplace safety standards.*

Keywords: *construction workers, silicate dust, survey, descriptive statistics*

1. INTRODUCTION

Over 3 million construction workers are exposed to silica dust in Europe, and in the United States of America, that number is 1.7 million construction workers (Sauvé et al., 2013). The construction industry represents one of the primary sources of air pollution (Cheriyana & Choi, 2020), where the dust that is created on construction sites is usually of natural origin, but still dangerous for the respiratory system. One of the most common types of dust present on construction sites is silicate dust (Mučenski, 2018). Exposure to dust on construction sites occurs during excavation, drilling, rock processing, tunneling, demolition of buildings, cutting and processing of concrete, brick, ceramic, and granite tiles, etc. (HSE UK, 2020). Silicate dust is a complex mixture of particles that vary in shape, size, and composition. The crystalline silicon is the most common form associated with the development of silicosis and other related diseases (Alabi & Bakare, 2011). The construction site is naturally loaded with dust particles, but the problem is when the free crystalline silica appears in the polluted air of a construction site. Once inhaled, it can pose various diseases such as silicosis, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, and lung cancer (Keramydas et al., 2020).

Silicosis is a lung disease caused by inhalation of dust containing particles of silicon dioxide, which are defined as "respirable", that is, the given form of silicon is called "respirable crystalline silicon" (RCS). Exposed workers may suffer not only from silicosis but also from certain cardiovascular diseases, sarcoidosis, pulmonary tuberculosis, lung infections, chronic obstructive disease, certain types of tumors, lung cancer, autoimmune diseases, and kidney disorders (Kreuzer et al., 2013). Various studies (Pérez-Alonso et al., 2014; Hoy et al., 2018) indicate that the occurrence of silicosis is directly related to the availability and proper use of personal protective equipment (PPE). Since the exposure to silica dust is continuously increasing, so is the

risk of mortality and increased mortality, making silica dust one of the major health problems worldwide (Requena-Mullor et al., 2021).

Although there is no adequate cure, preventive measures and a medical examination should be implemented (Requena-Mullor et al., 2021; OSHA, 2012). Silicosis, an incurable disease, requires quantitative and qualitative control of respirable crystalline silica and the development of appropriate control measures (Tavakol et al., 2016). HSE UK (2020) is proposing that when construction workers are exposed to chemical substances, in this case – silicate dust, there should be done risk assessment, risk control, and a review of the control measures. As the main preventive measures against silica dust, Mučenski (2018) proposes water curtains, extraction on the tool, organization of work tasks, ventilation, proper selection of PPE, and conducting health surveillance of exposed workers.

The aim of this research is to assess how construction workers perceive the level of awareness, risk perception, and use of PPE related to occupational exposure to silica dust through the use of survey and descriptive statistical analysis.

2. METHODOLOGY

With the aim of better understanding worker awareness of risks associated with silicate dust, quantitative research was conducted among construction workers in the form of a survey. The research was realized with an online survey that was created on the platform Google Forms, with full anonymity of respondents. The survey was composed of closed and semi-open questions, with a total number of 15 questions grouped into four sections:

1. Sociodemographic data – structured at the beginning of the questionnaire, with the aim of providing the segmentation of respondents according to gender, age, work experience in the construction industry and workplace on the construction site;
2. Awareness of silica dust – this section included questions about familiarity with the term silica dust, the effects that silica dust has on health, and to assess the risk of exposure to silica dust in the workplace;
3. The use of personal protective equipment (PPE) – this section included questions about provided PPE, use of PPE, types of PPE masks against dust, reasons for not wearing PPE
4. Health and safety (HSE) training, awareness and consequences of exposure to silica dust – information about the harmful effects of silica dust as a part of HSE training, information channels about silica dust, preventive measures against silica dust and adequacy of applied preventive measures against silica dust on construction site.

Most of the questions were in form with only one choice of answer, while some of the questions enabled multiple selections (checkbox type) or option “Other” for additional comments. Due to the impossibility of filling out the survey in online mode, the survey was printed and respondents were filling the survey manually on construction sites. After collecting the completed surveys, the results were uploaded using Google Forms. The target group consisted of construction workers and the data collection was done voluntarily. All of the construction workers were informed that the survey was anonymous and that collected data would be used only for the purpose of scientific research. The length of the survey was a couple of minutes.

Collected data is statistically processed and analyzed using descriptive statistics in order to analyze sociodemographic data, and identify patterns in risk perception, level of information, and frequency of use of PPE.

When analyzing the sociodemographic data, statistical analysis was conducted on two continuous variables in this study (age and work experience) to determine their arithmetic mean, median, and mode values. The standard statistical formulas were used for grouped data to calculate these measures because the data was presented in interval groups which required the use of class midpoints. The equations for arithmetic mean, median, and mode values are shown as follows. The arithmetic mean is calculated using the following equation (1):

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum(f_i \cdot x_i)}{\sum f_i}, \quad (1)$$

where f_i represents the frequency of the i -class, x_i represents the midpoint of the i -class and $\sum f_i$ represents the total number of observations.

The median class was calculated based on the cumulative frequency distribution using the equation (2):

$$Median = L + \left(\frac{\frac{N}{2} - F}{f_m} \right) * h, \quad (2)$$

where L represents the lower boundary of the median class, N represents the total number of observations, F represents cumulative frequency before the median class, f_m represents the frequency of the median class, and h width of the class interval.

The mode values were approximated as the midpoint of the most frequent class, using the equation (3):

$$Mode = \text{midpoint of modal class} \quad (3)$$

Patterns in risk perception, level of information, and frequency of use of PPE were displayed graphically by using bar graphs and pie charts. The applied method enabled clearer interpretation and understanding of collected results.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A survey about construction workers' awareness of the risks associated with silica dust was conducted on 55 male construction workers in Novi Sad. A survey about workers' awareness of the risks associated with silica dust was conducted on 55 male construction workers, where:

- 29.1% of workers were between 35-44 years old,
- 21.8% were between 45-54 years old,
- 21.8% were between 55-64 years old,
- 12.7% were between 18-24 years old,
- 9.1% were between 25-34 years old,
- 3.6% were 65 years old or older and
- only 1% were underage.

When talking about the working experience in the construction industry, 21.8% of respondents have been working between 16-20 years, 20% of respondents have been working between 6-10 years, 20% of respondents have been working between 1-5 years, 16.4% of respondents have been working between 11-15 years, 10.9% of respondents have been working between 21-30 years, while only 5.5% of respondents have been working for more than 31 years, and 5.5% of respondents have been working less than a year.

Based on collected data, the central tendencies – the mean, median, and mode were estimated for all analyzed continuous variables (age and work experience) in Table 1. The data shows that construction workers have an average age of 43.4 years and a median of 39 years thus indicating an older population on construction sites. Most participants fall within the 35-44 age range which places them in middle adulthood. The data indicates that participants on average have 13 years of work experience but the median value of 8 years demonstrates that fewer highly experienced respondents play a significant role in the average. The two main professional tenures of 16-20 years in the data represent the existence of two separate groups within the sample population for analysis. The sample's heterogeneity in these findings should be considered when conducting additional data analysis.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics – Central Tendencies of Age and Work Experience Among Construction Workers (n=55)

Variable	Arithmetic mean	Median	Mode	Additional notes
Age (years)	43.4	39	35-44	Based on grouped responses (n=55)
Work experience (years)	13.0	8	16-20	

The target group was construction workers exposed to silicate dust, so the largest representation is the construction workers who perform preparatory work as the main job on the construction site (47.3%), in addition, there are also other jobs such as painting and decorating works (23.6%), masonry works (9.1%), carpentry works (7.3%), earthworks (1.8%), concrete works (3.6%), reinforcement works (1.8%), ceramic works (1.8%), operating machines and equipment (1.8%), manual worker (1.8%).

Analyzing the section about construction workers' awareness of silica dust, the survey indicated some interesting facts. The construction workers had an assessment to evaluate their own knowledge about the definition of silica dust and its effects on human health from 1 to 5, where 1 was defined as completely unfamiliar, and 5 as very well-informed. The survey showed that most of the construction workers (49.1%) rated their knowledge with 2, which indicates a low level of information about this type of professional risk. On the other side, a small percentage of construction workers evaluated their knowledge with 4 (16.4%) and 5 (1.8%) showing that the percentage of construction workers who are aware of the risks and health consequences that silica dust can induce are negligible (Figure 1). When talking about the consequences that silica dust can induce on human health during long-term exposure to silicate dust, several different answers

were offered, some of which were incorrect, while some truly represented the consequences of exposure to silica dust, to see how familiar construction workers were. This question enabled multiple answers. Results showed that most of the construction workers are not informed (56.4%), while only 5.5% of construction workers are informed of silicosis as a health consequence (Figure 1). On the other hand, construction workers showed that they are familiar with the basic consequences after long-term exposure to silica dust because 10.9% of respondents stated bronchitis and 5.5% of respondents stated lung cancer as a source of consequence when being exposed to silica dust for a long time. By indicating skin allergies, high blood pressure, and headaches as a source of consequences during long-term exposure to silica dust, it was proven that familiarity with health consequences is low, and it should be improved by adapted HSE medicine lectures with the support of occupational medicine, all with the aim of increasing the awareness and knowledge of workers.

Figure 1: Familiarity with the term silica dust and its effects on health among construction workers (left) and the knowledge about consequences of long-term exposure to silica dust among construction workers (right)

At the final of this section, construction workers were asked to assess the risk of exposure to silica dust at their workplace (1-Very low risk, 5-Very high risk). Results showed that 38.2% of respondents assessed the risk as moderate (3), 23.6% of respondents estimated the risk as 2, and 23.6% with 4. A low number of respondents believe that the risk is very low (9.1%), while only 5.5% believe that the risk is very high (5). These results show that most of the construction workers perceive risk as present, but not extremely high, which can be due to lack of information during HSE training, lack of dust measurements, and lack of visually observable effects of exposure. Considering that the level of information and perception of silica dust as a risk represents an important aspect when assessing the awareness of construction workers, it is also important to assess their relation with the use of PPE. Effective health and safety system also depends on whether the protective equipment is provided by the employer. 38.2% of respondents stated that the PPE against silica dust is always provided and 61.8% of respondents stated that PPE against silica dust is provided only sometimes. In this section, the two questions drew attention to the sincerity of construction workers. Firstly, on the question: “Do you use a protective mask during work in a dusty environment?” most of the respondents (74.5%) said that they always use a protective mask when working in a dusty environment, and 25.5% of respondents stated that they use the protective mask sometimes when working in a dusty environment. On the other side, the question “If you don’t use a protective mask, what is the main reason for not wearing?” somehow revealed the real truth about the use of protective masks. As the main reason for not wearing a protective mask during work in a dusty environment, 36.4% of respondents revealed that the mask bothers them during the work (Figure 2)

Figure 2: The main reason for not using a protection mask among construction workers

Also, when talking about the type of personal protective mask that construction workers use when working in dusty environments, most of the workers stated that they use protective mask with basic protection from dust (FFP1), and a small percentage of respondents said that they are using the protective masks that provides better protection from dust and pollution. An interesting fact brought the attention when analyzing the collected

responses of the survey this question - 32.7% of respondents said that they are using ordinary surgical masks when working in dusty environments and 25.5% of respondents said that they don't know exactly what type of personal protective mask are using. In conclusion to this results, it is obvious that there is a gap between the use of PPE and the real awareness of its importance and correct application. Although most workers state that they are using PPE on a regular basis, additional questions reveal that inadequate types of masks are often used or that construction workers are not sure what equipment they are using. A significant percentage of construction workers complain about masks (bothering during work operations), which points to the need for ergonomic and functional adaptation of PPE. Therefore, workers are not irresponsible, but adequate information, equipment, and support are often not available for them. On the other side, employers and the HSE team should recognize the problems and act proactively (HSE training, availability of equipment).

The last section of the survey discovered the level of information among the construction workers across the formal HSE training, as well as the sources of information, the perception of existing preventive measures, and their opinions on the necessary preventive measures. When talking about the formal HSE training the survey showed that 63.6% of respondents stated that they were not informed about the harmful effects of silicate dust and protection measures against silica dust, and 36.4% of respondents stated that they were informed about the harmful effects of silica dust through HSE training. The survey showed that two main sources of information about hazards connected to silica dust are employers (through obligatory HSE training) and colleagues (Figure 3). The perception of existing preventive measures is shown in Figure 3. It is obvious that construction workers are aware that one of the existing preventive measures – The use of personal protective masks (FFP1, FFP2, FFP3) is necessary when working in a dusty environment (63.6%). Concerning fact is that 29.1% of respondents consider that surgical masks should be used as a preventive measure against silica dust.

Figure 3: Information sources about the risks associated with silicate dust among construction workers (left) and preventive measures for silica dust proposed by construction workers (right)

At the end of the survey, construction workers were asked to evaluate the adequacy of preventive measures against silica dust on the construction site where they work with a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means that preventive measures against silica dust are inadequate and 5 means that preventive measures against silica dust are adequate. Most of the respondents choose average values (3) as a neutral or medium rating, 27.3% with rate 4, 21.8% with rate 2, and the very low and very high rates are rare – rate 1 was given by only 1.8% of respondents, and rate 5 only 5.5% of respondents. This indicates that construction workers mostly think of preventive measures as something that is not completely inadequate, but also not completely satisfactory either. Most of the construction workers express moderate satisfaction, which means that there is a basic level of protection, but additional improvements are needed when applying preventive measures against silica dust.

4. CONCLUSION

The survey conducted among 55 male construction workers in Novi Sad demonstrates an insufficient understanding of silica dust health risks from prolonged exposure. Despite the fact that the surveyed population mostly contains middle-aged workers who possess extensive construction experience, they demonstrate limited comprehension of silica dust and their health impacts. The study reveals that only a small percentage of construction workers identified silicosis, bronchitis or lung cancer. Also, study showed that construction workers demonstrate a strong tendency to use PPE but their practice doesn't align with the actual level of provided protection. Workers either wear surgical masks or don't understand the proper kind of mask. Worker education about silica dust remains low due to inadequate program of HSE training, and most workers depend on co-workers to learn about the topic. Preventive measures are perceived as moderate, but the use of inadequate PPE and a general lack of risk perception highlight the necessity for better safety practices and improvement.

This research demonstrates an immediate requirement for: (1) specialized awareness initiatives and educational initiatives that address the particular dangers from silica dust, (2) both the accessibility and practicality of PPE, (3) strengthened the participation of employers and HSE teams in their ability to notice and resolve worker issues, (4) Monitoring and measuring dust level measurements and occupational health monitoring of workers who are exposed to silica dust, (5) Improving the worker education, attitudes and practices regarding silica dust exposure.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research has been supported by 'Karin Komerc' LLC, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia, which provided access to the construction site of 'VELEBIT Gradnja' LLC, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia, whose management and workers kindly agreed to participate in the study, and 'GAT' LLC, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia whose management and workers also kindly agreed to participate in the study. This research has been supported by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation (Contract No. 451- 03-137/2025-03/200156) and the Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad through project "Scientific and Artistic Research Work of Researchers in Teaching and Associate Positions at the Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad 2025" (No. 01-50/295). (V.M.) This research has been supported by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation through Contract No. 451-03-136/2025-03/200156. (J.T)

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